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Mooring System Integrity Management through Monitoring, Digital Twin and Control Technologies for Cost Reduction and Increased Efficiency

D6.4 Version 1.0

Closed Loop Control Strategies Definition v2

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Executive Summary

This report represents Deliverable D6.4 “Closed Loop Control Strategies Definition v2” of Work Package 6, “Integrity Management and Control Strategies”, of the EU H2020 project Mooring Sense.

The purpose of this deliverable is to describe the closed-loop control strategies that have been designed and implemented within the project. Two control loops are proposed and integrated into IKERLAN’s OpenDiscon open-source wind turbine controller code. The first control loop implements a method from the literature introducing torque demand variations to reduce blade pitch oscillations around rated wind speed. The second control loop makes use of a thrust force observer and the feedback of the smart sensor designed for the MooringSense project (platform and turbine position and attitude) to limit the thrust force in the turbine.

The mentioned observer description and validation is also provided in this document showing good correlation values between the estimated values and the values obtained from the simulation tools for different test cases.

Similarly, the control algorithms are explained, and their performance is validated using the platform and turbine modelled in SIMA software. Finally, it is shown that both proposed strategies help to mitigate the loads in the mooring lines and the FOWT (tower, blades, etc.) in terms of magnitude and cyclic loading, increasing the fatigue life expectation. However, generator torque variations are increased for turbulent wind conditions and power production must be reduced if the thrust limitation strategy is enabled.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Term	Description
ACT	Advanced Control Tool
AKF	Augmented Kalman Filter
BL4	Loss of 2 nd upper buoy from line 4
CLW4	Loss of clump weight from line 4
DLL	Dynamic linked library
FOWT	Floating offshore wind turbine
FRS	Fibre rope stiffness increased
FWT	Floating wind turbine
HMG	Healthy, with marine growth
HNMG	Healthy, without marine growth
LT	Locked turret
NL1	Loss of line 1
NMPZ	Non-minimum phase zeros

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose and scope

The purpose of this document is to describe the closed-loop control strategies that have been designed and implemented within the project. Detailed descriptions of the observer and control algorithms are included, as well as different simulations results to show their performance when estimating the status of the floating wind turbine and mitigating the dynamic loads on the system.

1.2 Intended audience / Classification

This is a public deliverable; thus, the document is intended for all interested readers.

1.3 Application documents

Inputs from the following documents were used as a source of information for preparing this document:

Table 1.1: Application documents

REF	Document
AD-01	Grant Agreement – 851703 - MooringSense
AD-02	Consortium Agreement – MooringSense

1.4 Reference Documents

The following documents were used as reference for preparing this report:

Table 1.2: Reference documents.

REF	Document
RD-01	D2.3 FOW Reference Case and Set up of the Baseline
RD-02	D2.5 Specifications and validation definition
RD-03	D3.2 Simulation dataset
RD-04	D3.7 Tank Testing Report

1.5 Document structure

The document is structured in the following sections:

- Section 2 provides the motivation and description of the developed thrust observer.
- Section 3 explains the closed-loop control algorithms developed in this task.
- Section 4 explains the simulations carried out to tests the performance of the observer and the control algorithms. The results for some of the simulations are shown and explained. Validation of the development is also provided in this section.

2. Observer

2.1 Motivation

One of the purposes of Task 6.2 is to develop a closed loop control strategy which limits the thrust force of the turbine. Nevertheless, a thrust force measurement from commercial sensors is not available. Consequently, an estimation of the latter from other available measurements becomes necessary.

The role of TNO in this task is to provide such an estimation, by making use of its control design tool: Advanced Control Tool (ACT). The ACT is a combination of several parts (models, controllers, filters, etc.), one of them being the design and implementation of an observer (also referred to as an estimator).

The observer estimates several variables that are not commonly available in wind turbines sensors. For the purposes of this work, the thrust force estimation \hat{F}_{ax} and the rotor effective wind speed estimation \hat{u}_{ax}^{rotor} are used, with the former being the one used for the purposes of closed loop floating wind turbine control.

The wind turbine controller developed in MooringSense also relies on accurate motion measurements of the floating wind turbine platform, which are provided by the smart sensor developed in WP4. On these measurements, state estimation techniques can be applied to retrieve the motions at the nacelle. In addition to the motions, information on estimated internal loads, such as tower base bending moments, can be valuable. For this reason, a second part of the advanced observer has been developed that provides estimates of the floating support structure motions and internal structural loads.

The InnWind 10 MW reference wind turbine model is used for the simulations here presented. The tower height is of 115.630 meters and the rotor radius of 89.181 meters. The turbine is geared with a gear ratio of 50. In terms of operating characteristics, the rated rotor speed corresponds to 9.6 RPM and the rated power to 10.64MW. The minimum and maximum rotor speeds are of 5 and 13 RPM. The cut-in and cut-out wind speeds are, respectively, 3 and 25 m/s.

The subsequent subsection describes the following:

- *2.2. Thrust observer description:* describes the main inner workings of the estimator, the necessary measurements which it uses to provide the signals estimates, the assumptions behind the modelling methodology chosen for the estimator as well as the values used.
- *2.3. Floating support structure observer:* describes the estimation of the motions and loads of the floating support structure using the smart sensor measurements.

2.2 Thrust observer description

The thrust observer is split into two main parts: (1) the first part estimates the states of the drive-train model, along with the aerodynamic torque, and (2) the second part estimates the rotor effective wind speed \hat{u}_{ax}^{rotor} and thrust force \hat{F}_{ax} . This is represented in Figure 2.1, where (1) is represented in block 'Kalman filter drive-train' and (2) is represented by the block 'Rotor effective aerodynamics'.

The estimator makes use of the available measurements, namely the generator torque T_{gen} , generator speed Ω_g and blade pitch angles θ . The former two are used in the Kalman Filter drive train to estimate the aerodynamic torque \hat{T}_a and the rotor speed $\hat{\Omega}_r$, which are then used, along with the blade pitch measurements to provide an estimate of the rotor effective wind speed \hat{u}_{ax}^{rotor} and thrust force \hat{F}_{ax} . The other estimated states are the shaft torque \hat{T}_{sh} and the shaft torsion angle $\hat{\gamma}$, which are not used for the purposes of this task.

Figure 2.1. Block diagram representing the observer input-output signals.

First, the estimation of the drive train states and aerodynamic torque is achieved by means of an Augmented Kalman Filter (AKF). The AKF makes use of a state space linear model based on the assumed linear structural dynamics of the drive train. The state space model for the discrete-time drive train model has the state vector $x_{dt} = [\gamma(k) \ \Omega_r(k) \ \Omega_g(k)]^T$. The measured output is the generator speed, hence the output matrix $C_{dt} = [0 \ 0 \ 1]$. The drive train model is augmented by a random walk model for the estimation of the aerodynamic torque \hat{T}_a and the final linear Kalman filter is used to estimate the state of the augmented system. The state of the augmented system becomes $x_{dt} = [\gamma(k) \ \Omega_r(k) \ \Omega_g(k) \ T_a^{sc}(k)]^T$, where T_a^{sc} is the scaled aerodynamic torque (scaled by the rotor inertia J_r for increased numerical robustness). In summary, the first estimation problem where the drive train Kalman filter is used boils down to reconstructing the shaft torsion angle γ , rotor speed Ω_r and aerodynamic torque T_a given the measured generator speed Ω_g and the generator torque T_{gen} . The generator speed measurement is disturbed by the sideways tower motion. This effect is considered negligible and not considered in the estimation problem.

Secondly, the block 'rotor effective aerodynamics' in the second step provides an estimate of the rotor effective wind speed \hat{u}_{ax}^{rotor} by means of inversion of the static torque equation $\hat{T}_a = \frac{1}{2} \pi R^3 (\hat{u}_{ax}^{rotor})^2 C_Q(\hat{\lambda}, \theta)$, where C_Q is the rotor torque coefficient, $\hat{\lambda} = R \hat{\Omega}_r / \hat{u}_{ax}^{rotor}$ is the tip speed ratio and R is the rotor radius. This block further gives an estimate of the axial force computed using the estimate \hat{u}_{ax}^{rotor} and the rotor thrust coefficient C_T .

Considering blade effective wind speeds and rotor-effective wind speed, the aerodynamic torque can be expressed as:

$$T_a = \frac{1}{2} \rho \pi R^5 \Omega_r^2 \frac{\frac{1}{B} \sum_{i=1}^B C_Q(\lambda, \theta^i)}{\lambda^2} \quad (2.1)$$

Where ρ is the air density and B the number of blades. Given the estimates of the aerodynamic torque \hat{T}_a and rotor speed $\hat{\Omega}_r$ from the drive-train state estimator, the following equation can be used for the estimation of the tip speed ratio:

$$\frac{\frac{1}{B} \sum_{i=1}^B C_Q(\lambda, \theta^i)}{\lambda^2} = \frac{2\hat{T}_a}{\rho \pi R^5 \Omega_r^2} \quad (2.2)$$

In general, the above equation has several solutions. To avoid multiple solutions, the search for λ is constrained only in an interval $\Lambda(\theta) = [\lambda_{min}(\theta), \lambda_{max}(\theta)]$, around the steady state (equilibrium) value for the tip speed ratio $\lambda^{eq}(\theta)$ that corresponds to the given pitch angle θ . The corners of this interval $\Lambda(\theta)$ are selected so that the function $C(\lambda, \theta)/\lambda^2$ is monotonous for all $\lambda_{min}(\theta) \leq \lambda \leq \lambda_{max}(\theta)$.

A unique solution to the above equation is found in an efficient and numerically reliable way and given an estimate $\hat{\lambda}$ of the tip speed ratio and the rotor speed estimate, $\hat{\Omega}_r$, the estimates of the rotor effective wind speed \hat{u}_{ax}^{rotor} and the thrust force \hat{F}_{ax} can be computed as follows:

$$\hat{u}_{ax}^{rotor} = \frac{\hat{\Omega}_r R}{\hat{\lambda}}, \quad (2.3)$$

$$\hat{F}_{ax} = \sum_{i=1}^B \hat{F}_{ax}^i(\hat{u}_{ax}^{rotor}) = \frac{1}{2} \rho \pi R^2 (\hat{u}_{ax}^{rotor})^2 \frac{1}{B} \sum_{i=1}^B C_T(\hat{\lambda}, \theta^i) \quad (2.4)$$

Note that this approach uses a flexible drive train observer, meaning that the drive train torsion is taken into account. The drive train torsion can be determined in two ways: either by specifying the shaft stiffness directly or by specifying the drive train torsional frequency, from which the drive train properties are then computed. A rigid drive train observer can also be chosen. For the design of the observer, the flexible model is used, as this was found to provide more accurate estimations when compared to the rigid one.

The values introduced here are for the DTU 10MW Reference Wind Turbine, which can be found in RD-01. In the drive train model:

- The fast shaft of the drive train model is assumed rigid, while the slow shaft is flexible and is modelled by a torsional stiffness s_{dt} and damping d_{dt} so as to model the frequency and damping of the first drive-train/collective lead-lag mode. The values used for the torsional stiffness and damping are respectively $5.2622 \cdot 10^8$ [Nm·rad⁻²] and 0.03 (ratio to critical).
- The gearbox is rigidly connected to the (rigid) nacelle, and has a transmission ratio of i_{tr} (positive when the rotation of the fast and slow shafts are the same and negative otherwise). The gearbox ratio value is of 50.
- The rotor J_r and generator J_g inertia values, taken into account in the equations of motion of the rotational dynamics of the two shafts, are respectively $1.56433 \cdot 10^8$ [Kg·m·m·rad⁻²] and $1.5005 \cdot 10^3$ [Kg·m·m·rad⁻²] (generator and fast shaft rotational inertia relative to the fast shaft).
- Losses are modelled by subtracting an equivalent torque T_{loss} from the aerodynamic torque in order to model conversion losses. This term is modelled by a Coulomb and viscous friction terms and a term proportional to the shaft torque. These terms are assumed to be negligible and hence set to zero.

2.3 Floating support structure observer

This second part of the advanced observer uses the smart sensor measurements (WP4) and the thrust estimate as described in the previous section to estimate the states of the floating support, representing the global motions (positions and velocities) of the platform rigid body modes and possible flexible body modes (such as tower deformation). These can be used to derive an estimate of the nacelle motions and support structure internal loading without direct load measurements.

As ideal sensors do not exist, measurements always contain undesired components like noise and drift in addition to the measured quantity of interest. Filtering can be applied to reduce noise from a

measurement signal, but has downsides such as delay. A well-known method for reducing noise on measurements is the Kalman filter, as also applied in the previously discussed thrust observer. With this method, knowledge of the underlying physics (model dynamics) and noise properties of the process and output are used to obtain clean estimates of the output.

A Kalman filter in its standard formulation assumes inputs to be known. In the case of the floating wind turbine support structure observer, the external forces from wind and waves are typically unknown. The axial thrust force from the wind can be replaced by the thrust estimate derived in the previous section. Wave loads on the floating support however will be considered as an unknown input, which makes this a problem of state estimation under (partially) unknown input excitation. The use of acceleration measurements also implies the system

Several methods for joint estimation of state and input have been developed and are available from literature. The method applied by Lourens et al [1] can be implemented using a straightforward extension of the standard Kalman filter and has been used in this task. The approach, as described in detail in [2], essentially adds an input estimation step preceding the traditional Kalman filter. In brief, the method follows the following procedure:

- 1) estimation of the unknown input
- 2) measurement update
- 3) time update

The reference system in MooringSense consists of the 10MW DTU RWT supported by the SATH platform of SAITEC with single point catenary chain/hybrid mooring. Figure 2.2 shows a picture and schematic representation of the floating wind turbine support structure. The measurements used are the motions of the floating platform (position s_{tb} , velocity v_{tb} and acceleration a_{tb}) and the SCADA of the wind turbine containing acceleration at the tower top (a_{tt}). The floating wind turbine support structure is described using a (set of) Linear Time Invariant (LTI) state space formulation. This requires some simplifications:

- The mooring dynamics are represented as a set of springs (k_M) acting on the mooring turret, linearized in the current operating point. These will be derived from precalculated stiffness tables for different positions of the platform.
- The hydrodynamic properties of the platform are represented by linearized stiffness and damping matrices (k_H, d_H) acting on the platform centre of gravity. These stiffness and damping properties and the added mass of the platform are derived from panel method diffraction calculations.
- The platform structural dynamics are modelled using a modal representation (interface modes and N_i internal modes). Currently the flexibility is limited to the wind turbine tower between floating platform and nacelle.
- The external wind excitation (F_A) is represented by the estimated thrust as described in the previous section.
- The external wave excitation (F_H) is modelled as an unknown input, either represented by 6DOF wave loads on the or by wave height and a set of 6DOF linearized wave forcing transfer functions.

For proper assessment of the described floating wind turbine support structure observer, a model that represents the smart sensor is required and under development. Therefore, verification and evaluation of the method using numerical simulations will be part of subsequent deliverables in WP6.

Figure 2.2. Drawing (left) and schematic (right) representation of the floating wind turbine support structure.

3. Closed-loop Control Strategies

This section describes the different control strategies that have been implemented and tested in the Mooring Sense project.

3.1 Introduction

IKERLAN's onshore wind turbine controller developed for the CL-Windcon project [3] has been used as a starting point for the developments of this project. It is a FAST compatible [4] controller, which is also compatible with SIMA, the software used for the modelling and simulation of the whole Mooring Sense project system: the floating wind turbine, the platform, and the mooring lines.

The mentioned controller code is called OpenDiscon and it is an open-source implementation of the DISCON interface, which was introduced by GHBladed and subsequently adopted by FAST and SIMA. OpenDiscon includes a drivetrain damper and torque and collective pitch control loops which are tuned to fit the onshore DTU 10MW wind turbine reference model. The CL-Windcon controller (OpenDiscon) block structure is shown in Figure 3.1 and it is based on IKERLAN's OpenWitcon, which is a generic wind turbine control code package.

Both, OpenDiscon and OpenWitcon are publicly available under version 3 of the General Public License. This licence allows anyone to contribute to their development, protects new contributions from being appropriated (and consequently being withdrawn from the public domain) by other users, including IKERLAN, as well as ensures that they are being appropriately attributed to their authors.

It is important to mention that only blade pitch control strategies are considered in this case, as SIMA performs the yaw control internally and does not follow yaw commands from the external controller interface.

The following paragraphs will explain the new developments added to the OpenDiscon controller to improve the performance, avoid unstable behaviours, and reduce loads on the FOWT of the Mooring Sense project.

3.2 Baseline Controller

Using onshore pitch control strategies as the one used in CL-Windcon, can cause severe instability due to the lower hydrodynamic stiffness of the water compared to the land configurations. Much research on control of FWT mention the *negative damping* phenomena in which the interaction between the blade pitch control system and the platform/tower motion causes oscillations in the blade pitch at rated wind speed [5], [6]. Figure 3.2 explains this phenomenon.

Figure 3.1. CL-Windcon controller block structure.

Figure 3.2. Negative damping cycle [7].

As stated by Boris Fischer [8], from a control engineering perspective, the mentioned behaviour is caused by a complex pair of non-minimum phase zeros (NMPZ) in the transfer function relating generator speed and blade-pitch angle. These zeros are also present on onshore wind turbines [9], but they are located at higher frequencies (near the natural frequency of the tower first natural bending moment). For FWT, they are located at low frequencies (close to the natural frequency of the platform pitch mode) [5] and are often excited causing the unstable behaviour.

Fischer also proposed the idea of compensating these NMPZ of the mentioned transfer function using another input (generator torque) and another output for the system (nacelle velocity in fore-aft direction) [8].

Figure 3.3. Using nacelle fore-aft velocity as feedback to compensate NMPZ.

Several adaptations have been considered when introducing Fischer's proposal into OpenDiscon controller:

1. Nacelle fore-aft or nodding velocity is usually not available in DISCON interface introduced by GHBladed. In this way, fore-aft acceleration can be integrated and used for this purpose.
2. A band pass filter has been included to remove the errors introduced by the integration process and ensure that the correction term works in the desired frequency range.

Figure 3.4 shows the blocks structure of the baseline controller which includes the torque correction computed from the nacelle fore-aft velocity.

Figure 3.4. Mooring Sense baseline controller block structure.

3.3 Thrust Limiter Controller

This section explains the control algorithm developed to fulfil the main objective of task 6.2 of the Mooring Sense project. As stated in the Grant Agreement, the proposed closed loop turbine control algorithms should take advantage of the real time motion measurements provided by the Mooring Sense project developed smart sensor (position, velocity, and attitude) to avoid the coupling of the platform surge, sway, pitch and roll motions with the generator speed regulator which can cause large resonant platform motions and high loads in the mooring lines, blades and tower [AD-01].

As seen in Figure 3.8, a thrust limitation control loop has been added to the baseline controller to calculate minimum blade pitch command values that would limit the maximum thrust force in the wind turbine. The method for the calculation of the blade pitch command for a desired thrust force relies on the following simple wind turbine model:

$$J \frac{\dot{\omega}}{b} = Q_a - b \cdot Q_g \quad (3.1)$$

Where J is the rotor inertia, ω is the generator speed, b is the gearbox ratio, Q_a is the aerodynamic torque and Q_g is the generator electric torque.

The aerodynamic torque can be calculated as:

$$Q_a = \frac{1}{2} \rho \cdot b \cdot \pi \cdot R^2 \cdot v^3 \cdot \frac{C_P(\lambda, \beta)}{\omega} \quad (3.2)$$

Where ρ and v are the air density and wind speed respectively, R is the generator rotor radius and C_P is the power coefficient for a given tip-speed ratio (λ) and blade pitch angle (β). The mentioned tip-speed ratio is also defined as follows:

$$\lambda = \frac{R \cdot \omega}{b \cdot v} \quad (3.3)$$

Using (3.3), (3.2) can be rewritten as:

$$Q_a = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \rho \cdot \pi \cdot R^5 \cdot \frac{C_P(\lambda, \beta)}{\lambda^3} \cdot \frac{\omega^2}{b^2} \quad (3.4)$$

$\frac{C_P(\lambda, \beta)}{\lambda^3}$ value can be then easily computed using equations (3.1) and (3.4) and the generator speed and torque received from the DISCON interface.

On the other hand, the thrust force on the wind turbine rotor can be calculated as:

$$T = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \rho \cdot \pi \cdot R^4 \cdot \frac{C_T(\lambda, \beta)}{\lambda^2} \quad (3.5)$$

$C_P(\lambda, \beta)$ and $C_T(\lambda, \beta)$ surfaces can be obtained launching multiple simulations for the studied onshore (DTU 10MW) wind turbine working at different operating points using FAST. Equivalent $\frac{C_P(\lambda, \beta)}{\lambda^3}$ and $\frac{C_T(\lambda, \beta)}{\lambda^2}$ surfaces can be then also computed and stored to be used as look-up tables.

The control algorithm proposed here uses these surfaces and equations above to estimate the blade pitch angle required to maintain a thrust force in two steps:

1. Firstly, the tip-speed ratio (λ) is estimated using equations (3.1) and (3.4) and $\frac{C_P(\lambda, \beta)}{\lambda^3}$ surface.
2. Then, the minimum blade pitch angle required is obtained using equation (3.5), $\frac{C_T(\lambda, \beta)}{\lambda^2}$ surface and the tip-speed ratio calculated in the previous step.

Figure 3.5 and Figure 3.6 show the precomputed $\frac{C_P(\lambda, \beta)}{\lambda^3}$ and $\frac{C_T(\lambda, \beta)}{\lambda^2}$ surfaces, while Figure 3.8, Figure 3.9 and Figure 3.10 and show the blocks structure of the thrust limiter controller which includes the control

loop explained above for the calculation of the minimum blade pitch angle required to maintain a maximum thrust force at the wind turbine rotor.

Figure 3.5 C_T/λ^2 and C_P/λ^3 contour curves.

Figure 3.6 C_T/λ^2 and C_P/λ^3 3D curves.

As shown in equation 3.5 and Figure 3.8, the thrust limitation approach that reduces the mooring lines loads requires a maximum thrust command to estimate a minimum blade pitch value. This maximum thrust value could be set manually (using the *external maximum thrust* input) or defined automatically by other means. A simulation postprocessing analysis method is proposed here for the maximum thrust command estimation.

Simulations have been performed to characterize the behaviour of the wind turbine, platform and mooring lines using the baseline controller and constant wind conditions for different incident directions (every 30 degrees) and speeds (4 to 25m/s). In this way, the platform position can be related to the turbine aerodynamic thrust for different working conditions. Another surface can be then obtained interpolating these points (see Figure 3.7).

A 2-dimensional look-up table can be then built setting a maximum thrust command for each position/displacement value using the following criteria:

- Position/displacement inside the limits obtained in the simulations: no thrust limitation. Maximum thrust value set to a high value (the maximum thrust value obtained in the simulations).
- Position/displacement outside the limits obtained in the simulations: thrust limitation activated setting a low value for the maximum thrust value (20% of the maximum thrust value obtained in the simulations to ensure that the resulting minimum pitch value is achievable).

The surface or 2D look-up table obtained is shown in the following picture:

Figure 3.7. Thrust [N] VS platform position [m] (simulation results: up-left / interpolation: up-right / thrust limits: down).

Figure 3.8. Mooring sense thrust limiter controller block structure.

Figure 3.9. Structure of *ikTsrEst* blocks.

Figure 3.10. Structure of *ikThrustLimEst* (left) and *ikThrustLim* (right) blocks.

4. Simulation and Validation

4.1 Observer simulation and validation

The observer is first tuned and tested in different simulation environments to test the accuracy of the thrust force estimation and investigate its limitations depending on the wind and wave conditions.

The subsequent subsections describe the following:

- *4.1.1. Tuning of observer gains:* describes the tuning of the Kalman filter parameters. The Kalman filter approach requires the tuning of two weights, the process noise covariance matrix \mathbf{Q} and the measurement noise covariance \mathbf{R} . These two are tuned so as to find the most appropriate balance that yields the most accurate thrust force estimation.
- *4.1.2. Simulations in OpenFAST:* describes the simulations in OpenFAST where the estimated thrust force is compared with the aerodynamic thrust force from OpenFAST. The accuracy of the estimator is assessed based on different simulations where degrees of freedom are increasingly added so as to better understand their influence on the estimation accuracy.
- *4.1.3. Merging of TNO's observer and IKERLAN's controller and simulations:* the communication procedure between IKERLAN's controller and TNO's observer is introduced. Simulations in SIMA are performed so as to evaluate the accuracy of the thrust force estimation with the final model, platform and mooring settings.

4.1.1 Tuning of observer gains

Two parameters can be tuned to improve the accuracy of the Kalman filter, the process noise covariance matrix \mathbf{Q} and the measurement noise covariance \mathbf{R} . \mathbf{Q} defines the variance of the input (the original state of the non augmented drive train model and the aerodynamic torque in the augmented drive train model) and \mathbf{R} defines the variance of the output (generator speed).

Different values are tested for the design of the estimator and two measures are evaluated: (1) the relative difference between the modelled thrust force and the estimated thrust force and (2) the correlation between the two time series, in order to ensure that the estimated signal is not delayed with relation to the true measurement.

The tuning of these parameters is based on simulations in ACT. The simulations in ACT compare the estimated thrust force yielded by the observer and the simulated thrust force. The simulated thrust force is taken as the sum of the blade-effective axial forces. The blade-effective axial forces are computed as:

$$F_{ax}^{(i)}(u_{ax}^{(i)}) = F_{dyn}(u_{ax}^{(i)}) C_T(\lambda^{(i)}, \theta^{(i)})/B \quad (4.1)$$

where the index i refers to one of the three blades, F_{dyn} is referred to as the generalized force and defined as:

$$F_{dyn}(v) = \frac{1}{2} \rho \pi R^2 v^2 \quad (4.2)$$

where v refers to the constant and undisturbed wind speed, R is the rotor radius, B the total number of the blades and $u_{ax}^{(i)}$ is the blade-effective axial wind speed. The latter contains both stochastic and deterministic effects:

$$u_{ax}^{(i)}(\psi^{(i)}) = u_{sto}^{(i)} - u_{mean}(\psi^{(i)}) + u_{shr}^{(i)}(\psi^{(i)}) + u_{shd}^{(i)}(\psi^{(i)}) + u_{str}^{(i)}(\psi^{(i)}) \quad (4.3)$$

where $u_{sto}^{(i)}$ refers to the stochastic wind speed signals for each of the blade, u_{mean} is the unscaled mean longitudinal wind speed and $u_{shr}^{(i)}$, $u_{shd}^{(i)}$ and $u_{str}^{(i)}$ represent deterministic effects, namely wind shear, tower shadow and tower blade motion.

The process noise covariance matrix \mathbf{Q} and the measurement noise covariance \mathbf{R} of the Kalman filter drive train are first set to a baseline value. The baseline value is changed, and different configurations of the observer are tested.

To evaluate the performance of the observer for different values of \mathbf{Q} and \mathbf{R} the average absolute relative deviation ε between the estimated and modelled thrust force is quantified, along with the correlation between the two signals ρ . The average absolute relative deviation ε is computed as follows:

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{N_k} \frac{|\hat{T}_{a_k} - T_{a_k}|}{T_{a_k}}}{N_k} \quad (4.4)$$

where \hat{T}_{a_k} is the estimated thrust force at time instant k , T_{a_k} is the modelled thrust force at time instant k taken as the ground truth, $|\hat{T}_{a_k} - T_{a_k}|$ is the absolute deviation at time instant k and N_k is the total number of samples retrieved from the simulation.

The baseline values are:

- $Q = \begin{bmatrix} 0.01 & 0 \\ 0 & 2500 \end{bmatrix}$
- $R = 0.1$

Two types of wind conditions are used. Both are realistic wind fields taking into account stochastic and deterministic components. Both wind fields have a mean wind speed of 13.5 m/s (1.25 times the InnWind 10MW turbine rated wind speed). The modelling approach for wind field generation is again based on the blade effective wind signals, i.e., per blade there is only one wind signal that parameterizes the corresponding blade axial force $F_{ax}^{(i)}$ and $T_a^{(i)}$.

In the first test only stochastic effects relating to the slowly varying rotor average wind (0P component) are considered. The latter wind conditions used in the simulation, as well as the comparison between modelled and estimated signals is represented in Figure 4.1. The results of the tuning of \mathbf{Q} and \mathbf{R} are summarized in Table 4.1. The blade effective wind speeds used in this first simulation are represented in the upper plot of Figure 4.3.

In the second test, periodic components with frequencies equal to multiples of the rotor's rotational frequency, $\Omega_r/2\pi$, resulting from rotational wind field sampling (nP components, $n=1, 2, \dots$). are included. Furthermore, wind shear and tower shadow effects are included. The wind conditions and the comparison between modelled and estimated thrust force using the baseline values of \mathbf{Q} and \mathbf{R} are presented in Figure 4.2. The results of the tuning of the \mathbf{Q} and \mathbf{R} gains are summarized in Table 4.2. The blade effective wind speeds used in this second simulation are represented in the lower plot of Figure 4.3.

The results in Table 4.1 and Table 4.2 show that the accuracy of the estimator is more sensitive to the value of \mathbf{R} than the value of \mathbf{Q} . Increasing the order of magnitude of the \mathbf{Q} covariance matrix appears not to have a significant impact in the accuracy of the estimations.

In addition, it is seen that for more realistic inflow conditions, with both stochastic and deterministic effects, the average absolute deviation between the modelled and estimated signals is maintained below 10%, with a correlation between signals above 90%.

Figure 4.1. Results of observer tuning using baseline gains for Kalman filter and first wind conditions. Error refers to the average absolute deviation between the modelled and estimated signals.

Table 4.1. Summary of results of tuning of Q and R for the first type of wind field (stochastic effects based on the 0P component and no deterministic effects).

Scenario	Q	R	ε [%]	ρ [%]
Baseline	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.01 & 0 \\ 0 & 2.5 \cdot 10^3 \end{bmatrix}$	0.1	1.89	99.44
#1	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.1 & 0 \\ 0 & 2.5 \cdot 10^4 \end{bmatrix}$	0.1	1.89	99.45
#2	$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 2.5 \cdot 10^5 \end{bmatrix}$	0.1	1.89	99.45
#3	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.01 & 0 \\ 0 & 2.5 \cdot 10^3 \end{bmatrix}$	0.01	1.89	99.45
#4	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.01 & 0 \\ 0 & 2500 \end{bmatrix}$	1	1.92	99.43
#5	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.01 & 0 \\ 0 & 2500 \end{bmatrix}$	10	2.02	99.37

Figure 4.2. Results of observer tuning using baseline gains for Kalman filter and second wind conditions.

Table 4.2. Summary of results of tuning of Q and R for the second type of wind field (stochastic effects based on the nP component and deterministic effects (wind shear and tower shadow))

Scenario	Q	R	ε [%]	ρ [%]
Baseline	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.01 & 0 \\ 0 & 2.5 \cdot 10^3 \end{bmatrix}$	0.1	8.57	93.40
#1	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.1 & 0 \\ 0 & 2.5 \cdot 10^4 \end{bmatrix}$	0.1	8.54	93.45
#2	$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 2.5 \cdot 10^5 \end{bmatrix}$	0.1	8.54	93.46
#3	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.01 & 0 \\ 0 & 2.5 \cdot 10^3 \end{bmatrix}$	0.01	8.54	93.45
#4	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.01 & 0 \\ 0 & 2500 \end{bmatrix}$	1	8.77	93.07
#5	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.01 & 0 \\ 0 & 2500 \end{bmatrix}$	10	9.35	92.03

Figure 4.3. Blade effective wind speed for the two wind conditions used in ACT simulations.

4.1.2 Simulations in OpenFAST

The observer is then tested in OpenFAST. The goal of this intermediary step is to increase the confidence in the observer estimates and understand its limitations when being exposed to aero-elastic simulations.

The controller used in this simulation was designed so that the maximum static axial force exerted on the rotor does not surpass 1.3 [MN] (peak shaving). The operating curves of the controller can be seen in Figure 4.4. The latter Figure depicts a comparison between the curves corresponding to the controller used where peak shaving is employed (orange) and without peak shaving (blue). This explains, for example, the fact that in the following simulation results the blades pitch at wind speed lower than rated wind speed.

For the simulations in OpenFAST, the FAST model of the DTU 10MW Reference Wind Turbine, onshore version 0.1, provided in the context of MooringSense is used.

Realistic winds are generated using TurbSim. An example of the input file using TurbSim has been attached in Appendix A. A time series of 1000 seconds is generated with a time step of 0.02. A grid with height of 200 meters and width of 200 meters is used. Hub height is set to 119 meters. A Kaimal turbulence model is used. Normal turbulence is chosen according to the IEC 61400 1-Ed3 edition. A power law wind profile is used with a power law exponent of 0.11. The height of the reference wind speed is set to hub height at 119 meters and the surface roughness length is set to default.

To generate different wind speed profiles only the mean (total) wind speed at the reference height is varied. The example shows a value of 6 meters per second.

As a starting point, the observer is tested in OpenFAST. Degrees Of Freedom (DOF) are turned on one at a time and the accuracy of the observer is evaluated. The latter evaluation follows a similar procedure as in using the ACT tool described in subsection 4.1.1. The estimation of thrust force is compared to the total rotor aerodynamic load (force in x direction), which corresponds to signal *RtAeroF_{xh}* extracted from the *AeroDyn* module. The wind profile with the above-mentioned characteristics is used, with a mean

total value of wind speed of 10 meters per second. Simulations with 700 seconds are performed, and the first 200 seconds are removed to avoid transient behaviour in the final analysis.

All DOF available in *ElastoDyn* and the corresponding settings are summarized in Table 4.3. The *FlapDOF1* and *FlapDOF2* correspond to the first and second flapwise blade modes DOF. The *EdgeDOF* is the first edgewise blade mode DOF. The *TeetDOF*, *DrTrDOF*, *GenDOF* and *YawDOF* are respectively the rotor-teeter DOF, drivetrain rotational flexibility DOF, generator DOF and yaw DOF. The *TwFADOF1* and *TwFADOF2* are, respectively, the first and second fore-aft tower bending mode DOF. The *TwSSDOF1* and *TwSSDOF2* are respectively the first and second side-to-side tower bending mode. The remaining DOFs refer to the platform motion, where *PltfmSfDOF*, *PltfmSwDOF* and *PltfmHvDOF* refer to the surge, sway and heave translation motions of the floating wind turbine. *PltfmRDOF*, *PltfmPDOF* and *PltfmYDOF* refer to the rotational DOFs, namely the platform roll, pitch and yaw. Since originally no mooring was specified in the OpenFAST model files, the platform surge and sway and yaw DOFs are always set to False (T in Table 4.3 refers to the logical setting True and F to the logical setting False). This is thought to be acceptable as the main goal of this intermediate step is to evaluate the impact of the natural frequencies of the drive train signals in the estimation accuracy. Note that the controller used for this test was not tuned for a floating turbine. However, since the goal of this analysis is to evaluate the observer accuracy and not so much as the controller performance, a controller tuned for a floating turbine is not needed at this point.

The baseline simulation where only the generator, yaw platform heave, roll and pitch are set to True is first performed. The results are depicted in Figure 4.5 and Figure 4.6. An average absolute deviation between the estimated and modelled (in OpenFAST) aerodynamic thrust force of 3.54% throughout the complete simulation is observed. The signals show a correlation coefficient of 93.27%.

The results for all simulations and the corresponding metrics used to quantify the accuracy of the estimated thrust force are summarized in Table 4.3. It can be seen that as more degrees of freedom are enabled in the simulation, the higher the error between the estimated and real thrust and the lower the correlation between the two signals.

An explanation for this is the resonance frequencies associated with the blade edgewise motion and the drive train torsion and the high sampling frequency of the signals (50Hz). For the first, it is seen that a natural frequency in the vicinity of 2Hz appears in the estimated thrust force, as depicted in Figure 4.7. This frequency was inexistent in the first 5 simulations. For the second, it is seen that the natural frequency of the shaft torsional mode is in the vicinity of 4Hz appears in the estimated thrust force, as depicted in Figure 4.8. This frequency was inexistent in the content of the signals in the first 6 simulations. Given that the estimator makes use of the generator torque, rotor speed and blade pitch angles to provide an estimate of the thrust force, the frequencies in these signals will be visible in the estimated thrust, despite the real aerodynamic thrust having no meaningful frequencies.

The natural frequencies of the edge wise blade mode and the drive train torsional mode have a detrimental effect in the accuracy of the estimated thrust force. In other words, although the relevant dynamics of the drive train are captured with the linearized model used in the estimator, due to the sampling frequency of 50Hz other frequency components may be captured which are not relevant for the rotor thrust force estimation. A possible way to circumvent this would be to filter these frequencies, nevertheless such filtering can introduce delay in the estimated signal, which could further decrease the signals correlation. Moreover, including both drive train and blade dynamics may increase the complexity of the observer, which is not desirable. In this line of reasoning, it was decided not to use additional filters as so far it has been found that the estimated thrust force matched the aerodynamic one in OpenFAST with satisfactory accuracy.

Figure 4.4. Controller operating curves (with and without peak shaving comparison).

Table 4.3. Degrees Of Freedom settings for each simulation in OpenFAST and corresponding evaluation of thrust force estimation.

Simulation	FlapDOF1	FlapDOF2	EdgeDOF	TeetDOF	DrTrDOF	GenDOF	YawDOF	TwFADOF1	TwFADOF2	TwSSDOF1	TwSSDOF2	ϵ [%]	ρ [%]
#1	F	F	F	F	F	T	T	F	F	F	F	3.54	93.27
#2	F	F	F	F	F	T	T	T	F	T	F	3.80	92.41
#3	F	F	F	F	F	T	T	T	T	T	T	3.77	92.56
#4	T	F	F	F	F	T	T	T	T	T	T	2.76	94.61
#5	T	T	F	F	F	T	T	T	T	T	T	3.00	93.67
#6	T	T	T	F	F	T	T	T	T	T	T	3.77	89.74
#7	T	T	T	F	T	T	T	T	T	T	T	4.47	85.97

Figure 4.5. Wind turbine main signals for OpenFAST baseline simulation. Comparison with observer estimates of the aerodynamic thrust force. Main DOF disabled.

Figure 4.6. Wind turbine main signals for OpenFAST baseline simulation in the frequency domain. Comparison with estimated rotor aerodynamic thrust force in the frequency domain.

Figure 4.7. Comparison of relevant signals in the frequency domain for simulation number 6 (blade edgewise degree of freedom enabled).

Figure 4.8. Comparison of relevant signals in the frequency domain for simulation number 7 (drive train torsion degree of freedom enabled).

4.1.3 Simulations in SIMA

The controller to be used makes use of the thrust force estimations yielded by the observer. The observer is first compiled into a Dynamic Link Library (DLL). Within the controller toolchain, the observer DLL is called. Based on the measured signals, the thrust force will be estimated by the observer and is given back to the turbine controller.

This interface is then tested in Simulation Workbench for Marine Applications (SIMA) and the accuracy of the estimated thrust force is again evaluated by using the deviation and correlation metrics, as before. The controller used was the *baseline_SIMA* available in IKERLAN's public repository at the time the simulations were performed (see subsection 4.2.2 for details on getting the controller).

For the simulations, the simplistic and realistic wind field, similarly as the ones generated for the OpenFAST simulations are used (stationary uniform and 3-dimensional turbulent wind fields). The waves are modelled using a Jonswap model, where the significant wave height H_s [m] and T_p [s] are set depending on the mean wind speed and relations in the available reference document [RD-03]. Simulations of 4200 seconds are performed, where the first 600 are removed leaving the last 3600s for the analysis.

The results of all simulations are summarized in Figures 4.9, 4.10, 4.11 and 4.12, with the former two referring to simulations with a static inflow and the latter two referring to simulations with a turbulent realistic wind field. The parameters used for each one of the simulations are fully detailed in Table 4.4 and Table 4.5, with the former referring to a simulation with a static inflow and the latter referring to simulations with a turbulent realistic wind field.

Generally speaking, for both static inflow wind profiles and realistic ones, the relative deviation of the thrust force tends to be below 15% and the correlation higher than 79%.

For static inflow wind profiles, the estimations are naturally more accurate, with deviations lower than 6% for all wind speed simulations and correlations higher than 90%. For the realistic wind profile, the accuracy of the estimations is lowest near rated wind speed. A minimum value of 3.80% is found for a mean wind speed at reference height of 10 meters per second, increasing in a linear fashion and reaching the highest value of 13.43% for a mean wind speed of 20 m/s.

No significant differences in the estimator performance were found when comparing cases with waves and without waves. For the static inflow simulations small deviations were found for wind speeds higher than 14 m/s. However, the differences were only marginal and of 0.29 percentual points for a mean wind speed of 16 m/s, 0.41 percentual points for a mean wind speed of 18 m/s and 0.3 percentual points for a mean wind speed of 20 m/s. For the simulations with realistic inflow profiles no significant differences were found.

Simulation results in the time and frequency domain for the static inflow wind profile of 16 meters per second without waves are shown in Figures 4.13, 4.14, 4.15 and 4.16. Simulation results in the time and frequency domain for the static inflow wind profile of 16 meters per second with waves are shown in Figures 4.17, 4.18, 4.19 and 4.20.

Simulation results in the time and frequency domain for the realistic turbulent 3D inflow wind profile with mean wind speed of 16 meters per second without waves are shown in Figures 4.21, 4.22, 4.23 and 4.24. Simulation results in the time and frequency domain for the realistic turbulent 3D inflow wind profile with mean wind speed of 16 m/s with waves are shown in Figures 4.25, 4.26, 4.27 and 4.28.

Figure 4.9. Comparison of average relative deviations between estimated and measured thrust force in SIMA for simulations with stationary inflow of different mean wind speeds, with and without waves.

Figure 4.10. Comparison of correlation between estimated and measured thrust force in SIMA for simulations with stationary inflow of different mean wind speeds, with and without waves.

Figure 4.11. Comparison of average relative deviations between estimated and measured thrust force in SIMA for simulations with realistic 3D inflow of different mean wind speeds, with and without waves.

Figure 4.12. Comparison correlation between estimated and measured thrust force in SIMA for simulations with realistic 3D inflow of different mean wind speeds, with and without waves.

Table 4.4. Summary of results of estimator accuracy based on simulations in SIMA. Simulations using stationary inflow profile and both cases with waves and no waves.

Test			Wind Conditions											Wave conditions						Results		
Test details			Wind Speed							Shear		Wind Direction		Normal Wave			Swell Wave			Current	Thrust	
	time	rt	Type	Value [m/s]	Turbulence Model	IEC charact.	IEC standard	IEC type	TI [%]	Type	Exponent	RH	[deg]	Type	Hs [m]	Tp [s]	Type	Hs	Tp	[m/s]	Error [%]	Corr [%]
#1	4200	600	Stationary uniform	6									0	Jonswap	-0	10	-	-	-	-	5.88	99.74
#2	4200	600	Stationary uniform	8									0	Jonswap	-0	10	-	-	-	-	3.59	99.79
#3	4200	600	Stationary uniform	10									0	Jonswap	-0	10	-	-	-	-	3.44	99.70
#4	4200	600	Stationary uniform	12									0	Jonswap	-0	10	-	-	-	-	3.19	99.21
#5	4200	600	Stationary uniform	14									0	Jonswap	-0	10	-	-	-	-	2.51	98.08
#6	4200	600	Stationary uniform	16									0	Jonswap	-0	10	-	-	-	-	1.87	96.11
#7	4200	600	Stationary uniform	18									0	Jonswap	-0	10	-	-	-	-	1.96	93.37
#8	4200	600	Stationary uniform	20									0	Jonswap	-0	10	-	-	-	-	2.57	90.71
#9	4200	600	Stationary uniform	8									0	Jonswap	1.38	5.5	-	-	-	-	3.58	99.67
#10	4200	600	Stationary uniform	10									0	Jonswap	1.62	5.5	-	-	-	-	3.43	99.58
#11	4200	600	Stationary uniform	12									0	Jonswap	1.90	5.5	-	-	-	-	3.22	98.68
#12	4200	600	Stationary uniform	14									0	Jonswap	2.23	7.5	-	-	-	-	2.56	97.36

Testing with simplistic conditions

#13	4200	600	Stationary uniform	16								0		Jonswap	2.62	7.5	-	-	-	-	2.16	95.60
#14	4200	600	Stationary uniform	18								0		Jonswap	3.04	8.5	-	-	-	-	2.37	94.05
#15	4200	600	Stationary uniform	20								0		Jonswap	3.50	8.5	-	-	-	-	2.87	92.69

Table 4.5. Summary of results of estimator accuracy based on simulations in SIMA. Simulations realistic 3D wind fields generated in TurbSim (with different wind speed mean values) and both cases with waves and no waves.

Test			Wind Conditions											Wave conditions						Results			
Test details			Wind Speed							Shear		Wind Direction		Normal Wave			Swell Wave			Current	Thrust		
	time	rt	Type	Value [m/s]	Turbulence Model	IEC charact.	IEC standard	IEC type	TI [%]	Type	Exponent	RH	[deg]	Type	Hs [m]	Tp [s]	Type	Hs	Tp	[m/s]	Error [%]	Corr [%]	
#16	4200	600	Turbulent 3D Realistic simulations based on site characteristics	6	IECKAI	A	1-Ed3	NTM	26.933	Power law	0.11	119	0									5.43	97.30
#17	4200	600		6	IECKAI	A	1-Ed3	NTM	26.933	Power law	0.11	119	0		Jonswap	1.17	5.5	-	-	-		5.48	97.28
#18	4200	600		8	IECKAI	A	1-Ed3	NTM	23.200	Power law	0.11	119	0									4.19	98.42
#19	4200	600		8	IECKAI	A	1-Ed3	NTM	23.200	Power law	0.11	119	0		Jonswap	1.38	5.5	-	-	-		4.22	98.40
#20	4200	600		10	IECKAI	A	1-Ed3	NTM	20.960	Power law	0.11	119	0									3.79	98.08
#21	4200	600		10	IECKAI	A	1-Ed3	NTM	20.960	Power law	0.11	119	0		Jonswap	1.62	5.5	-	-	-		3.80	98.06

#22	4200	600	Turbulent 3D	12	IECKAI	A	1-Ed3	NTM	19,467	Power law	0.11	119	0										4.45	97.29
#23	4200	600	Turbulent 3D	12	IECKAI	A	1-Ed3	NTM	19,467	Power law	0.11	119	0		Jonswap	1.90	5.5	-	-	-			4.56	97.21
#24	4200	600	Turbulent 3D	14	IECKAI	A	1-Ed3	NTM	18,400	Power law	0.11	119	0										6.02	93.87
#25	4200	600	Turbulent 3D	14	IECKAI	A	1-Ed3	NTM	18,400	Power law	0.11	119	0		Jonswap	2.23	7.5	-	-	-			6.12	93.95
#26	4200	600	Turbulent 3D	16	IECKAI	A	1-Ed3	NTM	17,600	Power law	0.11	119	0										8.26	89.14
#27	4200	600	Turbulent 3D	16	IECKAI	A	1-Ed3	NTM	17,600	Power law	0.11	119	0		Jonswap	2.62	7.5	-	-	-			8.43	89.64
#28	4200	600	Turbulent 3D	18	IECKAI	A	1-Ed3	NTM	16,978	Power law	0.11	119	0										10.81	83.08
#29	4200	600	Turbulent 3D	18	IECKAI	A	1-Ed3	NTM	16,978	Power law	0.11	119	0		Jonswap	3.04	8.5	-	-	-			11.01	84.76
#30	4200	600	Turbulent 3D	20	IECKAI	A	1-Ed3	NTM		Power law	0.11	119	0										13.43	78.58
#31	4200	600	Turbulent 3D	20	IECKAI	A	1-Ed3	NTM		Power law	0.11	119	0		Jonswap	3.5	8.5	-	-	-			13.73	81.25

Figure 4.13. Comparison of estimated thrust from observer and thrust force signal from SIMA. Simulation results from test case #6: static inflow conditions with mean wind speed of 16 m/s, no shear and no waves. Comparison of thrust force zoomed in for 30 seconds in interval.

Figure 4.14. Wind turbine main signals. Simulation results from test case #6: static inflow conditions with mean wind speed of 16 m/s, no shear and no waves.

Figure 4.15. Platform movement main signals. Simulation results from test case #6: static inflow conditions with mean wind speed of 16 m/s, no shear and no waves.

Figure 4.16. Platform acceleration main signals. Simulation results from test case #6: static inflow conditions with mean wind speed of 16 m/s, no shear and no waves.

Figure 4.17. Comparison of estimated thrust from observer and thrust force signal from SIMA. Simulation results from test case #13: static inflow conditions with mean wind speed of 16 m/s and no shear. Jonswap model used with significant height of 2.62 meters and peak period of 7.5 seconds. Comparison of thrust force zoomed in for 60 seconds interval.

Figure 4.18. Wind turbine main signals. Simulation results from test case #13: static inflow conditions with mean wind speed of 16 m/s and no shear. Jonswap model used with significant height of 2.62 meters and peak period of 7.5 seconds.

Figure 4.19. Platform movement main signals. Simulation results from test case #13: static inflow conditions with mean wind speed of 16 m/s and no shear. Jonswap model used with significant height of 2.62 meters and peak period of 7.5 seconds.

Figure 4.20. Platform acceleration main signals. Simulation results from test case #13: static inflow conditions with mean wind speed of 16 m/s and no shear. Jonswap model used with significant height of 2.62 meters and peak period of 7.5 seconds.

Figure 4.21. Comparison of estimated thrust from observer and thrust force signal from SIMA. Simulation results from test case #26: realistic turbulent 3D wind field with mean wind speed of 16 m/s. No waves. Comparison of thrust force zoomed in for 60 seconds.

Figure 4.22. Wind turbine main signals. Simulation results from test case #26: realistic turbulent 3D wind field with mean wind speed of 16 m/s. No waves.

Figure 4.23. Platform movement main signals. Simulation results from test case #26: realistic turbulent 3D wind field with mean wind speed of 16 m/s. No waves.

Figure 4.24. Platform movement accelerations signals. Simulation results from test case #26: realistic turbulent 3D wind field with mean wind speed of 16 m/s. No waves.

Figure 4.25. Comparison of estimated thrust from observer and thrust force signal from SIMA. Simulation results from test case #27: realistic turbulent 3D wind field with mean wind speed of 16 m/s. Jonswap model used with significant height of 2.62 meters and peak period 7.5 seconds. Comparison of thrust force zoomed in for 70 seconds interval.

Figure 4.26. Wind turbine main signals. Simulation results from test case #27: realistic turbulent 3D wind field with mean wind speed of 16 m/s. Jonswap model used with significant height of 2.62 meters and peak period of 7.5 seconds.

Figure 4.27. Platform movement main signals. Simulation results from test case #27: realistic turbulent 3D wind field with mean wind speed of 16 m/s. Jonswap model used with significant height of 2.62 meters and peak period of 7.5 seconds.

Figure 4.28. Platform acceleration main signals. Simulation results from test case #27: realistic turbulent 3D wind field with mean wind speed of 16 m/s. Jonswap model used with significant height of 2.62 meters and peak period of 7.5 seconds.

The results shown compare the estimated and measured thrust forces that are made available by the observer and in SIMA, respectively, at each 0.02 seconds. Nevertheless, in a realistic application, it is foreseen that the controller will make use of the available thrust estimation at a lower time scale. Therefore, it can be hypothesized that the accuracy of the estimation, when compared at a lower timescale, is improved.

This hypothesis is tested by comparing both zero-phase filtered signals. A zero-phase low pass digital Butterworth filter is designed and used to filter the thrust force signal from SIMA and the estimated by the observer from an original sampling frequency of 50 Hz. Keeping in mind the goal of removing the high frequency components from both signals, a normalised cut off frequency of 0.004 is chosen. This corresponds to a frequency higher than the wind turbine 1P frequency, which is expected to be in the vicinity of 0.16Hz (9.6 RPM/60). A cut-off frequency of 0.2 Hz is then chosen (which corresponds to a normalised frequency of 0.04 (0.2/50)).

Making use of the signals from the test case #27 (realistic turbulent 3D inflow conditions with waves), the error decreases from 8.43% in the comparison of the unfiltered signals to 3.39% for the comparison with filtered signals. The correlation between the signal increases from 89.64% to 97.85%. A zoomed in comparison of the two signals, for both the unfiltered and filtered versions, can be seen in Figure 4.29. A comparison in the frequency domain can be seen in Figure 4.30.

Figure 4.29. Comparison between thrust force signals (estimated signal and SIMA signal) for the 50Hz original ones (upper plot) and the filtered version (lower plot).

Figure 4.30. Comparison between thrust force signals in the frequency domain (estimated signal and SIMA signal) for the 50Hz original ones (upper plot) and the filtered version (lower plot).

For future developments of the observer, it would be of interest to perform thrust force estimations on a real experiment and evaluate if such estimation can be used for real time control applications of floating wind turbines.

4.2 Controller Simulation and Validation

4.2.1 Simulation Tests Procedure

The closed-loop control strategies explained in section 3 were implemented into OpenDiscon controller code. SIMA software was then used for the testing and validation using the model of the SATH platform and the DTU 10MW wind turbine prepared by SINTEF Ocean. Details about SIMA software and the model used for the simulations can be found in RD-03.

Figure 4.31. Screenshot of the 3D view of the SIMA model.

Winds and wave directions have been defined following RD-01 for Buchan Deep site (see Figure 4.32, Figure 4.33 and Figure 4.34):

- Wind direction: 210 degrees.
- Waves and current direction: 0 degrees.

Figure 4.32. Layout of the mooring system (main incidence direction = waves direction) [RD-01].

Figure 4.33. Wind rose for 1-hour average wind speed 100m above sea level for the period 1980-2010 at Buchan Deep [RD-01].

Figure 4.34. All-year wave rose at Buchan Deep for the period 1958-2010 [RD-01].

4.2.2 Getting and using the controller

4.2.2.1 Getting Baseline Controller

As stated in previous paragraphs, IKERLAN's wind turbine controller code has been used as a basis for the development of the Mooring Sense project controllers. The mentioned controller code is called OpenDiscon and it is an open-source implementation of the DISCON interface, which was introduced by GHBladed and subsequently adopted by FAST and SIMA. OpenDiscon is based on IKERLAN's OpenWitcon, which is a generic wind turbine control code package.

Both, OpenDiscon and OpenWitcon are publicly available under version 3 of the General Public License. This licence allows anyone to contribute to their development, protects new contributions from being appropriated (and consequently being withdrawn from the public domain) by other users, including IKERLAN, as well as ensures that they are being appropriately attributed to their authors.

There are two different branches of the OpenDiscon project containing the implementation of the baseline controller explained in paragraph 3.2 publicly available in a GitHub repository. The details of each version are described below:

- **FAST version:** https://github.com/ikcontrol/OpenDiscon/tree/mooringSense_baseline_FAST
Fischer's method uses the nacelle pitch acceleration in this case. This nacelle pitching acceleration is passed through record 83 of Bladed interface.
- **SIMA version:** https://github.com/ikcontrol/OpenDiscon/tree/mooringSense_baseline_SIMA
The Fischer's method used to correct the pitch oscillations around rated wind speed uses the nacelle pitch angle. The correct nacelle pitch is calculated from two nacelle points coordinates passed from SIMA to the controller using a Java wrapper. It also requires an input file to be able to calculate the coordinate systems changes (see paragraph 4.2.2.3.2 for more information).

NOTE: Do not forget to initialize and update the submodules used by the OpenDiscon project (OpenWitcon).

4.2.2.2 Getting Thrust Limiter Controller

Similarly to the aforementioned baseline controller, the thrust limiter controller has been implemented using DISCON's open-source implementation OpenDiscon. It also uses OpenWitcon and all the new developments are publicly available under version 3 of the General Public License as well.

A new branch has been created inside OpenDiscon Mooring Sense project to allocate the code and dependencies required for the thrust limiter controller explained in paragraph 3.3 to work. This branch is publicly available in the same GitHub repository:

- https://github.com/ikcontrol/OpenDiscon/tree/mooringSense_thrustLimit_SIMA

The code included there is also prepared to work with SIMA simulation workbench distributed by SINTEF. Again, go to paragraph 4.2.2.3.2 for more information about using the controller code.

NOTE: Do not forget to initialize and update the submodules used by the OpenDiscon project (OpenWitcon).

4.2.2.3 Using the controller

4.2.2.3.1 Controller code compilation

The project must be compiled to get an appropriate `.dll` library which FAST/SIMA can call to run the control algorithms. Run `cmake` software pointing to the directory in which the Github repository has been cloned/downloaded, checkout to the desired branch and generate the appropriate project for the desired compiler (MinGW, Visual Studio, etc.). Make sure that `DISTRIBUTION=DISCON` and

CONFIGURATION=simple (baseline controller) or CONFIGURATION=MooringSense (thrust limiter) when generating the project.

4.2.2.3.2 Communication between SIMA and the controller

When starting using SIMA it was found that it had a limited implementation of the DISCON interface (for example, it does not include the nacelle nodding acceleration required by the Fischer's method implemented in the baseline controller). The standard SIMA input to the controller is limited to the parameters listed below:

- Status (record #1).
- Current time (record #2).
- Current time step (record #3).
- Number of blades (record #61).
- Blade 1 pitch angle (record #4).
- Blade 2 pitch angle (record #33).
- Blade 3 pitch angle (record #34).
- Measured generator speed (record #20).
- Measured rotor speed (record #21).
- Measured electrical power output (record #15).
- Hub wind speed (record #27).
- Tower top fore-aft acceleration (record #53).
- Tower top side-to-side acceleration (record #54).

SIMA DISCON interface had to be improved using a java wrapper to add additional register containing extra information required by the control algorithms:

- On the one hand, the first tests of the baseline controller were performed using tower top fore-aft acceleration as an equivalent measurement for the nacelle nodding movement and it showed the expected pitch movement damping behaviour when there were no platform or nacelle yawing movements. However, if the turbine yaws during the simulations the difference between tower top and nacelle fore-aft accelerations does not allow the correction of the unstable behaviour. For this reason, the coordinates of two points of the nacelle and the platform yawing displacement had to be used to compute the real nacelle nodding movements required by the Fischer's method.
- Turret/platform position (or displacement) and attitude is also required by the thrust limiting strategy to decide the maximum allowed thrust. These measurements should be provided by the smart sensor. However, it was not possible to include a virtual version of the smart sensor in the simulation environment during the validation procedure (virtual implementation of the smart sensor and its measurement errors will be carried out in future stages of the Mooring Sense project). For this reason, position and attitude values provided by SIMA simulation software through DISCON interface were used for the simulation tests.

The final list of registers included using the java wrapper and used by the implemented controllers is:

- Time (register #2)
- Communication interval (register #3)
- Measured generator speed (register #20)
- Measured generator torque (register #23)
- Tower top fore-aft acceleration (register #53)

- Nacelle X displacement in the shaft reference system (register #83)
- Tower top X displacement in the global reference system (register #84)
- Locking turret displacement X (register #120)
- Locking turret displacement Y (register #121)
- Locking turret displacement Z (register #122)
- Platform yaw displacement (register #123)
- Platform pitch displacement (register #124)
- Platform roll displacement (register #125)
- Platform yaw speed (register #126)
- Platform pitch speed (register #127)
- Platform roll speed (register #128)
- Nacelle point 1 X displacement (register #129)
- Nacelle point 1 Y displacement (register #130)
- Nacelle point 1 Z displacement (register #131)
- Nacelle point 2 X displacement (register #132)
- Nacelle point 2 Y displacement (register #133)
- Nacelle point 2 Z displacement (register #134)

Where nacelle points 1 and 2 are located at the same height one at the front and the other at back of the nacelle respectively:

Figure 4.35 Schematic of nacelle points location.

As SIMA interface only sends to the java wrapper the points displacement from their initial position, the real initial position must be introduced to the controller. For this reason, an input file is required to make these values easily accessible for modification. An example of the input file required by the controller is shown in Figure 4.36.

```

1 C:\MOORING_SENSE\SimulationResults\1_ConstWind_IkThrustLimiter.bin
2 1 -- Save output flag (0: No, Other value: Yes)
3 0 -- Initial heading (in degrees)
4 0 -- Initial nacelle yaw (in degrees)
5 0 -- Wind direction (in degrees)
6 -70.66 -- Platform reference system X coordinate in GLOBAL system
7 0 -- Platform reference system Y coordinate in GLOBAL system
8 70.66 -- Turbine reference system X coordinate in parent system
9 0 -- Turbine reference system Y coordinate in parent system
10 2.637 -- Nacelle point 1 (closer to the rotor, nacBack in SIMA) X coordinate in local system
11 0 -- Nacelle point 1 (closer to the rotor, nacBack in SIMA) Y coordinate in local system
12 2.737 -- Nacelle point 2 (nacFront in SIMA) X coordinate in local system
13 0 -- Nacelle point 2 (nacFront in SIMA) Y coordinate in local system
14 C:\MOORING_SENSE\ControllerInputs\surfacesFiles\cplambda3.bin
15 C:\MOORING_SENSE\ControllerInputs\surfacesFiles\ctlambda2.bin
16 C:\MOORING_SENSE\ControllerInputs\surfacesFiles\thrustLimitSurface.bin
17 C:\MOORING_SENSE\SimulationResults\1_ConstWind_IkThrustLimiter.txt
18

```

Path to a binary file in which variables can be logged to analyse the controller behaviour in detail.

Path to binary files containing the C_p , C_t , λ^3 , λ^2 and $T(x, y)$ curves required by the thrust limiter control.

Path to a text file in which the controller can output error messages.

Figure 4.36. Example of the controller input file.

Find the appropriate java wrapper version and its dependencies inside the *SIMA_deps* folder which can be found inside the SIMA version branch (*dllWrapper_MSense.jar* file). The different surfaces (.bin files) and the thrust observer (compiled .dll) can be also found inside *deps* when using the thrust limiter controller.

4.2.3 Simulation and Testing Results

The following subsections show the results for the simulations carried out with the developed controllers.

4.2.3.1 Baseline Controller SIMA Simulation Results

Figure 4.37 to Figure 4.45 show the results for the simulations carried out to evaluate performance of the implemented baseline controller introduced in section 3.2, compared to the CL-Windcon controller taken as a reference. Both, constant and turbulent winds have been used to test the behaviour of the controller.

As seen in the constant wind simulation figures, the behaviour of the baseline controller is the same for low and high wind speeds (8m/s and 25m/s respectively). However, when reaching rated wind speed (between 11 and 12m/s), the baseline controller manages to reduce the oscillations caused by the NMPZ explained in paragraph 3.2. The achieved reduction in blades and platform pitching movements and lines stress will result in less fatigue damage and increased life, especially for blade pitch actuators and mooring lines.

On the other hand, when working with turbulent winds, it is more difficult to see the benefits of the proposed baseline controller due to the high turbulence of the used wind model (turbulent wind modelled as defined in RD-03). A small reduction in the peaks of the blades pitch angle can be also seen when analysing the blade pitch movements in detail (see Figure 4.44), whereas torque and electrical generated power oscillations have been clearly increased. This drawback, which was also mentioned by Fischer in [8], is caused by the torque term introduced to reduce the nacelle pitch oscillations around rated wind speed and results in a higher usage of the generator torque and increase in the drive train loads.

Figure 4.37. Baseline controller VS CL-Windcon controller performance comparison for constant wind at 8m/s.

Figure 4.38. Baseline controller VS CL-Windcon controller performance comparison for constant wind at 11.5m/s.

Figure 4.39. Baseline controller VS CL-Windcon controller performance comparison for constant wind at 12m/s.

Figure 4.40. Baseline controller VS CL-Windcon controller performance comparison for constant wind at 25m/s.

Figure 4.41. Baseline controller VS CL-Windcon controller performance comparison for turbulent wind at 8m/s mean wind speed.

Figure 4.42. Baseline controller VS CL-Windcon controller performance comparison for turbulent wind at 10m/s mean wind speed.

Figure 4.43. Baseline controller VS CL-Windcon controller performance comparison for turbulent wind at 12m/s mean wind speed.

Figure 4.44. Baseline controller VS CL-Windcon controller performance comparison for turbulent wind at 12m/s mean wind speed (detail).

Figure 4.45. Baseline controller VS CL-Windcon controller performance comparison for turbulent wind at 24m/s mean wind speed.

4.2.3.2 Baseline Controller Tank Testing Results

The baseline controller was provided to SINTEF Ocean as a dynamic linked library (DLL) for the basin tank tests. However, as explained in RD-04, zero accelerations were fed into OpenFAST so tower-top acceleration was not received by the controller and no motion compensation strategy was applied. Nevertheless, the platform pitch motions were in any case stable for all tests.

Figure 4.46 shows the platform and tower pitch measurements for most critical test carried out in the basin tank (test 4021, rated wind speed). The main benefits of the NMPZ compensation strategy of the baseline controller were not tested, but the figure shows a stable behaviour of the system.

Figure 4.46. Basin test 4021 results.

4.2.3.3 Thrust Limiter Controller SIMA Simulation Results – HMG Condition

This paragraph shows the main results obtained for one of the simulation reference cases defined in RD-03: healthy system status with marine growth. Figure 4.47 to Figure 4.51 show the comparison of the baseline controller and the thrust limiter controller performance for different wind conditions. As seen in the figures, the behaviour of both controllers is very similar, especially for lower wind speeds. However, higher blade pitch angles are obtained for wind speeds greater than 10m/s (see Figure 4.50 to get more detail at 12m/s). This mentioned increase in the blade pitch angles (less than 1 degree for the mentioned case) results in a small reduction of the platform pitch and mooring lines maximum stress forces (around 7% reduction for the highest peak values).

More detail of the benefits of using the thrust limiter controller will be shown in section 4.2.3.4 where the controller is evaluated for damaged system conditions.

Figure 4.47. Baseline controller VS Thrust limiter controller performance comparison for turbulent wind at 8m/s mean wind speed.

Figure 4.48. Baseline controller VS Thrust limiter controller performance comparison for turbulent wind at 10m/s mean wind speed.

Figure 4.49. Baseline controller VS Thrust limiter controller performance comparison for turbulent wind at 12m/s mean wind speed.

Figure 4.50. Baseline controller VS Thrust limiter controller performance comparison for turbulent wind at 12m/s mean wind speed (detail).

Figure 4.51. Baseline controller VS Thrust limiter controller performance comparison for turbulent wind at 24m/s mean wind speed.

4.2.3.4 Thrust Limiter Controller SIMA Simulation Results – Constant Wind, Line Removed

This section shows the results obtained for different simulations in which one of the mooring lines of the system has been removed. The benefits of the thrust limiter controller are clearly shown here.

Figure 4.52 to Figure 4.67 show some of the results obtained for the simulations. Figure 4.52 to Figure 4.55 show the comparison between the baseline controller and the thrust limiter controller when line 1 is removed. Around rated wind speeds (Figure 4.53 and Figure 4.54), when the aerodynamic thrust and consequently the stress in the lines is higher, the thrust limiter controller gets clearly into action: blades pitch angles are increased to values around 8 to 10 degrees resulting in a reduction of the stress forces in the lines to values below 1MN (peaks of 2MN and 1.5MN with the baseline controller). Furthermore, not only the maximum stress forces are reduced, but also the cyclic loading is damped faster resulting in a reduction in the fatigue damage for the lines. It is also important to mention that, because of the aerodynamic thrust limitation, the generator speed and the generated power is also reduced.

On the other hand, Figure 4.56 to Figure 4.67 show the analysis for the simulations carried out removing the different mooring lines (one at each time) and using constant wind with different incident directions. All simulations results show that, when the thrust limitation approach is used, the platform/turret displacement is reduced decreasing the stress in the mooring lines. These figures also show that, as the thrust limit depends on the platform position and the nacelle heading, the reduction in the lines stress depends also on the direction and it is lower for directions around 60°, 180°, 300° (directions between every two pairs of lines).

Figure 4.52. Baseline controller VS Thrust limiter controller performance comparison for constant wind at 8m/s mean wind speed and missing mooring line 1.

Figure 4.53. Baseline controller VS Thrust limiter controller performance comparison for constant wind at 11.5m/s mean wind speed and missing mooring line 1.

Figure 4.54. Baseline controller VS Thrust limiter controller performance comparison for constant wind at 12m/s mean wind speed and missing mooring line 1.

Figure 4.55. Baseline controller VS Thrust limiter controller performance comparison for constant wind at 25m/s mean wind speed and missing mooring line 1.

Figure 4.56. Mooring line 1 broken (NL1 constant wind) - Aerodynamic thrust and lines maximum axial force VS platform displacement (XY) – Baseline controller (up) VS Thrust limiter controller (down).

Figure 4.57. Mooring line 1 broken (NL1 constant wind) - Platform displacement, aerodynamic thrust and lines maximum axial force VS Wind Speed – Baseline controller (up) VS Thrust limiter controller (down).

Figure 4.58. Mooring line 2 broken (NL2 constant wind) - Aerodynamic thrust and lines maximum axial force VS platform displacement (XY) – Baseline controller (up) VS Thrust limiter controller (down).

Figure 4.59. Mooring line 2 broken (NL2 constant wind) - Platform displacement, aerodynamic thrust and lines maximum axial force VS Wind Speed – Baseline controller (up) VS Thrust limiter controller (down).

Figure 4.60. Mooring line 3 broken (NL3 constant wind) - Aerodynamic thrust and lines maximum axial force VS platform displacement (XY) – Baseline controller (up) VS Thrust limiter controller (down).

Figure 4.61. Mooring line 3 broken (NL3 constant wind) - Platform displacement, aerodynamic thrust and lines maximum axial force VS Wind Speed – Baseline controller (up) VS Thrust limiter controller (down).

Figure 4.62. Mooring line 4 broken (NL4 constant wind) - Aerodynamic thrust and lines maximum axial force VS platform displacement (XY) – Baseline controller (up) VS Thrust limiter controller (down).

Figure 4.63. Mooring line 4 broken (NL4 constant wind) - Platform displacement, aerodynamic thrust and lines maximum axial force VS Wind Speed – Baseline controller (up) VS Thrust limiter controller (down).

Figure 4.64. Mooring line 5 broken (NL5 constant wind) - Aerodynamic thrust and lines maximum axial force VS platform displacement (XY) – Baseline controller (up) VS Thrust limiter controller (down).

Figure 4.65. Mooring line 5 broken (NL5 constant wind) - Platform displacement, aerodynamic thrust and lines maximum axial force VS Wind Speed – Baseline controller (up) VS Thrust limiter controller (down).

Figure 4.66. Mooring line 6 broken (NL6 constant wind) - Aerodynamic thrust and lines maximum axial force VS platform displacement (XY) – Baseline controller (up) VS Thrust limiter controller (down).

Figure 4.67. Mooring line 6 broken (NL6 constant wind) - Platform displacement, aerodynamic thrust and lines maximum axial force VS Wind Speed – Baseline controller (up) VS Thrust limiter controller (down).

4.2.3.5 Thrust Limiter Controller SIMA Simulation Results – NL4M Condition

This paragraph shows the main results obtained for one of the simulation reference cases defined in RD-03: loss of line loss at T=1500s (without marine growth). Figure 4.68 to Figure 4.77 show the comparison of the baseline controller and the thrust limiter controller performance for different wind conditions. The thrust limiter controller performance for the healthy condition is also shown in the figures to remark the effect of the damage.

As seen in the figures, the behaviour of both controllers is very similar for high and low wind speeds. However, the effect of thrust limiter controller action is clearly shown around rated wind speed (between 10 and 12 m/s). Figure 4.70 to Figure 4.75 show that, for $T > 1500$ s, the blade pitch action is increased and higher pitch values are applied. This mentioned increase in the blade pitch angles results again in a reduction of the mooring lines stress forces, especially for lines 3, 5 and 6, which are the most stressed ones due to the loss of line 4. These lines stress range and mean are reduced, resulting in a lower fatigue damage to protect their lifetime while maintaining the power production.

Turbulent wind. NL4M. No marine growth - Mean wind speed = 8 m/s

Figure 4.68. Baseline controller VS Thrust limiter controller performance comparison for NL4M condition (mean wind speed = 8 m/s).

Turbulent wind. NL4M. No marine growth - Mean wind speed = 8 m/s

Figure 4.69. Baseline controller VS Thrust limiter controller lines forces comparison for NL4M condition (mean wind speed = 8 m/s).

Figure 4.70. Baseline controller VS Thrust limiter controller performance comparison for NL4M condition (mean wind speed = 10 m/s).

Turbulent wind. NL4M. No marine growth - Mean wind speed = 10 m/s

Figure 4.71. Baseline controller VS Thrust limiter controller lines forces comparison for NL4M condition (mean wind speed = 10 m/s).

Figure 4.72. Baseline controller VS Thrust limiter controller performance comparison for NL4M condition (mean wind speed = 12 m/s).

Turbulent wind. NL4M. No marine growth - Mean wind speed = 12 m/s

Figure 4.73. Baseline controller VS Thrust limiter controller lines forces comparison for NL4M condition (mean wind speed = 12 m/s).

Figure 4.74. Baseline controller VS Thrust limiter controller performance comparison for NL4M condition (mean wind speed = 12 m/s) (detail).

Figure 4.75. Baseline controller VS Thrust limiter controller lines forces comparison for NL4M condition (mean wind speed = 12 m/s) (detail).

Figure 4.76. Baseline controller VS Thrust limiter controller performance comparison for NL4M condition (mean wind speed = 24 m/s).

Turbulent wind. NL4M. No marine growth - Mean wind speed = 24 m/s

Figure 4.77. Baseline controller VS Thrust limiter controller lines forces comparison for NL4M condition (mean wind speed = 24 m/s).

4.2.4 Validation

The closed loop control algorithms have been validated following the procedures defined in RD-02. Both the baseline and thrust limiter controllers have been tested and validated using SIMA software and the baseline controller has been also used in the Ocean Basin tests showing a stable behaviour.

As shown in the previous paragraphs, the self-excitation or 'negative-damping' phenomenon is avoided by the baseline controller using the method proposed by Fischer [8] and the mooring line loads are reduced for the worst-case scenarios (damaged working conditions) using the thrust limitation approach. On the other hand, when using the thrust limitation, power production is reduced to decrease stress in the mooring lines in terms of maximum load and cyclic loading causing fatigue damage. In addition, Fisher's method causes an increased torque cyclic loading in the generator, especially when working with turbulent winds.

5. Conclusions and Future Work

This deliverable gives detailed description of the observer and control algorithms implemented for MooringSense project FOWT. On the one hand, the developed observer, which uses an Augmented Kalman Filter and the rotor aerodynamic model to estimate the rotor effective wind speed and the thrust force, is described in detail. On the other hand, two additional control loops are described and added to IKERLAN's OpenDiscon wind turbine onshore controller with the purpose of reducing dynamic loads on the system (mooring lines, platform, tower, blades, etc.). The first proposed loop follows the strategy introduced by Fischer in [8] to reduce blades pitch oscillations when reaching rated wind speed, whereas the second loop introduces a novel strategy to control the wind turbine using maximum thrust commands. This thrust limitation approach makes use of the feedback of the smart sensor defined for the MooringSense project and the thrust force estimated by the mentioned observer to decide proper thrust commands.

Both, observer and controller algorithms, have been implemented and tested using different simulation tools (OpenFAST and SIMA) and models publicly available or provided by other project partners. Simulation and validation of the observer is shown in section 4.1, where the accuracy and correlation between the observer estimated thrust force and OpenFAST or SIMA thrust force is calculated. Simulations in OpenFAST show relative average deviations between 3.5% and 4.5% and correlation values between 93.3% and 85.6%. The former values depend on the simulation and respective degrees of freedom used in each one. For simulations in SIMA using realistic three-dimensional turbulent inflow, the relative average deviations show values within the interval of 3.8% and 13.4% and correlation values between 98.1% and 78.6%. The values found depend mostly on the incoming wind speed and are not sensitive to wave characteristics. The proposed control algorithms (Fischer's method and thrust limitation) have also been tested using SIMA. Simulation procedure and results are shown in section 4.2, where the performance of both loops is explained. Both proposed methods help to mitigate the loads in the mooring lines and the FOWT (tower, blades, etc.) in terms of magnitude and cyclic loading, increasing the fatigue life expectation. However, Fischer's method also increases generator torque variations, and the thrust limitation approach reduces power production. The performance of the baseline controller including only Fischer's control loop in the water tank campaign is also presented, showing a stable behaviour during the tests.

Altogether, the different analyses and concepts introduced have provided new prospects in operating floating offshore wind turbines in an optimized way.

Future work will focus on implementing the advanced closed loop control strategies here presented in real life basin tests so as to increase the technology readiness level of this solution. In this way, real smart sensor measurements feedback could be also used for testing the proposed control strategies and the effect of the measurements error could be analysed. Further investigation on the trade-off between decreased fatigue loads and decreased power production should be carried out to understand the net benefit of increased life expectancy for the turbine.

6. References

- [1] E. M. Lourens, G. Lombaert, C. Papadimitriou, and G. De Roeck, “Joint estimation of states and input in linear structural dynamics,” May 2011.
- [2] S. Gillijns and B. De Moor, “Unbiased minimum-variance input and state estimation for linear discrete-time systems,” *Automatica*, vol. 43, pp. 934–937, 2007, doi: 10.1016/j.automatica.2006.11.016.
- [3] A. Mayssara A. Abo Hassanin Supervised, “CL-Windcon D2.1 – Minimal loading wind turbine de-rating strategy and active yaw controllers,” 2014. [Online]. Available: <http://www.clwindcon.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/03/CL-Windcon-D2.1-Wind-turbine-controllers.pdf>.
- [4] “National Wind Technology Center’s Information Portal | Wind Research | NREL,” 2013. <https://www.nrel.gov/wind/nwtc.html> (accessed Sep. 17, 2021).
- [5] T. Larsen and T. Hanson, “A method to avoid negative damped low frequent tower vibrations for a floating, pitch controlled wind turbine,” *J. Phys. Conf. Ser.*, vol. 75, p. 12073, 2007, doi: 10.1088/1742-6596/75/1/012073.
- [6] J. M. Jonkman, “Influence of Control on the Pitch Damping of a Floating Wind Turbine,” 2008, Accessed: Sep. 17, 2021. [Online]. Available: <http://www.osti.gov/bridge>.
- [7] D. Ward, M. Collu, and J. Sumner, “Reducing Tower Fatigue through Blade Back Twist and Active Pitch-to-Stall Control Strategy for a Semi-Submersible Floating Offshore Wind Turbine,” 2019, doi: 10.3390/en12101897.
- [8] B. Fischer, “Reducing Rotor Speed Variations of Floating Wind Turbines by Compensation of Non-Minimum Phase Zeros,” *Renew. Power Gener. IET*, vol. 7, pp. 413–419, 2013, doi: 10.1049/iet-rpg.2012.0263.
- [9] W. E. Leithead and S. Dominguez, “Coordinated Control Design for Wind Turbine Control Systems,” vol. 2006, 2006.

Appendix A : TurbSim input files for realistic wind profile generation

```
TurbSim Input File. Valid for TurbSim v1.06.00, 31-Aug-2017; IEC Kaimal spectrum, DTU 10MW RWT

-----Runtime Options-----
123456 RandSeed1 - First random seed (-2147483648 to 2147483647)
789012 RandSeed2 - Second random seed (-2147483648 to 2147483647) for intrinsic pRNG, or an alternative pRNG: "RanLux" or "RNSNLW"
False WbMHTP - Output hub-height turbulence parameters in GenPro-binary form? (Generates RootName.bin)
False WbFHTP - Output hub-height turbulence parameters in formatted form? (Generates RootName.dat)
False WbADHH - Output hub-height time-series data in AeroDyn form? (Generates RootName.hh)
True WbADFF - Output full-field time-series data in TurbSim/AeroDyn form? (Generates RootName.bts)
True WbLFF - Output full-field time-series data in SLADED/AeroDyn form? (Generates RootName.wnd)
False WbADTHR - Output tower time-series data? (Generates RootName.twr)
False WbFMTFF - Output full-field time-series data in formatted (readable) form? (Generates RootName.u, RootName.v, RootName.w)
False WbACT - Output coherent turbulence time steps in AeroDyn form? (Generates RootName.cts)
True Clockwise - Clockwise rotation looking downwind? (used only for full-field binary files - not necessary for AeroDyn)
0 ScaleIEC - Scale IEC turbulence models to exact target standard deviation? [0=no additional scaling; 1=use hub scale uniformly; 2=use individual scales]

-----Turbine/Model Specifications-----
20 NumGrid_Z - Vertical grid-point matrix dimension
20 NumGrid_Y - Horizontal grid-point matrix dimension
0.02 TimeStep - Time step [seconds]
1000.0 AnalysisTime - Length of analysis time series [seconds] (program will add time if necessary: AnalysisTime = MAX(AnalysisTime, UsableTime+GridWidth/MeanHHWS) )
1000.0 UsableTime - Usable length of output time series [seconds] (program will add GridWidth/MeanHHWS seconds)
119.00 HubHt - Hub height [m] (should be > 0.5*GridHeight)
200.00 GridHeight - Grid height [m]
200.00 GridWidth - Grid width [m] (should be >= 2*(RotorRadius+ShaftLength))
0 VFlowAng - Vertical mean flow (uplift) angle [degrees]
0 HFlowAng - Horizontal mean flow (skew) angle [degrees]

-----Meteorological Boundary Conditions-----
"IECKAI" TurbModel - Turbulence model ("IECKAI"=Kaimal, "IECVKM"=von Karman, "GP_LLJ", "NWTCP", "SMOOTH", "WF_UPW", "WF_07D", "WF_14D", "TIDAL" or "NONE")
1-E03 IECstandar - Number of IEC 61400-x standard (x=1,2, or 3 with optional 61400-1 edition number (i.e. "1-E02") )
"4" IECturbc - IEC turbulence characteristic ("4", "8", "16" or the turbulence intensity in percent) ("NHFS" option with NWTCP, not used for other models)
NTM IEC_WindType - IEC turbulence type ("NTM"=normal, "xETM"=extreme turbulence, "xEM1"=extreme 1-year wind, "xEM50"=extreme 50-year wind, where x=wind turbine class 1, 2, or 3)
default ETM - IEC ETM "c" parameter [m/s] (or "default")
PL WindProfileType - Wind profile type ("JET", "LOG"=logarithmic; "PL"=power law; "H2L"=Log law for TIDAL spectral model; "IEC"=PL on rotor disk, LOG elsewhere; or "default")
119 RefHt - Height of the reference wind speed [m]
6 URef - Mean (total) wind speed at the reference height [m/s]
350 ZJetMax - Jet height [m] (used only for JET wind profile, valid 70-490 m)
0.11 PLExp - Power law exponent (or "default")
default Z0 - Surface roughness length [m] (or "default")

-----Non-IEC Meteorological Boundary Conditions-----
57.45 Latitude - Site latitude [degrees] (or "default")
0.05 RICH_NO - Gradient Richardson number
default UStar - Friction or shear velocity [m/s] (or "default")
default ZI - Mixing layer depth [m] (or "default")
default PC_Uw - Mean hub u'w' Reynolds stress (or "default" or "none")
default PC_Uv - Mean hub u'v' Reynolds stress (or "default" or "none")
default PC_Uw - Mean hub u'w' Reynolds stress (or "default" or "none")
default IncDec1 - u-component coherence parameters (e.g. "10.0 0.3e-3" in quotes) (or "default")
default IncDec2 - v-component coherence parameters (e.g. "10.0 0.3e-3" in quotes) (or "default")
default IncDec3 - w-component coherence parameters (e.g. "10.0 0.3e-3" in quotes) (or "default")
default CohExp - Coherence exponent (or "default")

-----Coherent Turbulence Scaling Parameters-----
".\EventData" CTEventPath - Name of the path where event data files are located
random CTEventFile - Type of event files ("random", "1e" or "dis")
true Randomize - Randomize disturbance scale and location? (true/false)
1.0 DistScl - Disturbance scale (ratio of dataset height to rotor disk).
0.5 CTly - Fractional location of tower centerline from right (looking downwind) to left side of the dataset.
0.5 CTb - Fractional location of hub height from the bottom of the dataset.
30.0 CTStartTime - Minimum start time for coherent structures in RootName.cts [seconds]

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NOTE: Do not add or remove any lines in this file!
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